

In urban debates, the right to the city represents a call to a collective exercise over urbanization, through a perspective that exceeds individual rights, going beyond the simple access to city services [7]. On the contrary, it is actually the "right to change ourselves by changing the city more after our heart's desire" [7]. This perspective, by recognizing the ongoing disputes within urban policies, also helps to think how things could be otherwise.

The right to the city

the body-territory expands the way of seeing [2], helping to think about what is left behind as well. Maybe what is being (systematically) ignored would enable the invention of other ways of life [6] in the cities.

Thus, in this short text, I share those thoughts about how body-territory spotlights what big data miss. Identifying what is being lost makes room for thinking about the kind of city we want to live in and, as a consequence, the sort of people we want to be. Let's start this debate by thinking about the places our bodies inhabit. In that case, we can better visualize our priorities for a city open to a diversity of bodies and existences, where memory, pleasure, care, affection, and feelings should also inform datafied decisions.

When data are removed from their corresponding context, something is gone. Thus, if urban policies become based mainly on big data, it is vital to question what stories have been informing decisions that impact life in cities. By making visible the implications of the body as territory,

Big data epistemologies advocate that data reflects reality, generates the most valuable knowledge, and informs the best decisions about the world [5]. With this in mind, what is the place in the city for the web of relations that overflows the body, I ask this question while I think about the relations, memories, oppressions, affections, and feelings that arise when we inhabit our bodies and its neighborhoods.

Urban big data

References

- [1] See the "Bodies Territories" card of The Oracle for Transfeminist Technologies, by Coding Rights, at transfeministech.codingrights.org
- [2] Gago, V. (2020). *Feminist International: How to Change Everything*. Verso.
- [3] Cruz-Hernández, D. T. (2016). Una mirada muy otra a los territorios-cuerpos femeninos. *Solar*, 12(1), 35-46.
- [4] Kitchin, R. (2018). Data-driven urbanism. In Kitchin, R., Lauriault, T. P., & McArdle, G. (Eds.). *Data and the City* (pp. 44-56). Routledge.
- [5] Ricaurte, P. (2019). Data Epistemologies, the Coloniality of Power, and Resistance. *Television & New Media*, 20(4), 350-365.
- [6] Britos-Castro, A. & Zurbruggen, S. (2022). Narrar(nos) desde el cuerpo territorio. *Nuevos apuntes para un pensamiento situado y metodologías en contexto*. *Ánfora*, 29(52), 43-70.
- [7] Harvey, D. (2008). The Right to the City. *New Left Review*, 53, 23-40.

It is not solely about my body, of course, but about the complexity of all bodies inhabiting the world.

That is why **body-territory** (or *cuerpo-territorio*) has been helping me understand the mesh enacted within the increasing use of big data to make urban policy decisions.

Body-territory may be described as an idea-call arising from indigenous, peasant and feminist struggles in Latin America. It calls attention to the continuity and reciprocity between the "individual" body and the collective body and between the human body and the territory [2, 3].

With cities becoming more networked places [4], where big data emerges as a priority in urban management, it is relevant to ask what happens to the body(-territory) in a datafied city.

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**the world(s)
inhabits
every body**

**seeing
the body
in the
datafied
city**

The very idea of carrying with me the territories I inhabit or have inhabited [1] makes me think about the web of affections, memories, and feelings that involve the act of existing in the world. The entanglements in this net result from relations and exchanges between my body and places, groups, human and nonhuman, living and nonliving elements [2].

what to ask to start talking about

WORLD

what is the first place I occupy
in the world?

what places do I have
to struggle to get into or be in?

what worlds do I touch when
I live in my home, my neighborhood, my city?